

Improving working memory performance in healthy older adults: Investigating the training effects on central executive through a quasi-experimental approach

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Abstract

Introduction: Working memory (WM) training is widely recognized as an effective intervention to enhance WM capacity in the elderly. This study aims to explore the impact of WM training on both criterion and near-transfer tasks in older adults.

Method: Utilizing a quasi-experimental design, this research involved 30 participants aged 60 to 83. Participants were randomly allocated into two active training groups and one control group. Active Group 1 underwent 20 training days, each lasting 30 minutes, while Active Group 2 received 15 minutes of Cogmed WM training per session over 25 days. The control group participated in assessments but did not receive training. All groups were evaluated on criterion and near-transfer tasks before and after the training.

Results: The data indicated that Active Group 2 exhibited slight improvements in criterion task performance compared to both Active Group 1 and the control group. In near-transfer tasks, particularly the backward digit span task, Active Group 2 also outperformed the other groups.

Discussion: The findings reinforce the potential for WM enhancement in older adults through targeted training. Additionally, the study highlights that training specific WM subsidiaries can foster transfer effects to untrained central executive functions, underscoring the adaptability and plasticity of aging cognitive systems.

Take-home message: WM remains trainable and plastic amongst healthy older adults in the Moroccan setting.

Keywords: aging; older adults; transfer effect; working memory.

INTRODUCTION

Working Memory (WM) refers to the capacity to store and manipulate information over short periods [1]. WM is critically involved in various cognitive processes, including reading comprehension, reasoning, and problem-solving [2,3]. It is well-established that WM capacity tends to decline with age [4]. This age-related decline in WM is known to contribute to changes in fluid intelligence [5]. Evidence suggests that WM training can be an effective and affordable strategy to counteract age-related cognitive declines [6-8].

WM training has been demonstrated to be effective not only in typically developing children and those with developmental challenges (such as Down syndrome, learning difficulties, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder) but also in older adults [9-11]. However, the results of WM training studies remain contentious regarding performance improvements on transfer tasks [5,6,8]. This controversy is attributed to the variety of programs used, the duration and frequency of training sessions [12,13], and the specific WM domains targeted [14].

A notable study by Gao et al. [15] revealed that focusing on the executive domain of WM during training sessions yields greater improvements than targeting other WM domains. These findings contrast with those reported by Brum et al. [14], who found that three sessions of verbal WM training, each lasting 30 to 40 minutes, can enhance overall cognition. According to Brum et al. [14], the group that received training significantly outperformed the control group in post-tests and maintained these benefits six months after training concluded.

In alignment with existing literature on WM training in aging [2,8,12-15], the present study explores the trainability of WM in a sample of older adults. Two key questions are addressed from this perspective: (A) Can WM subsidiaries be effectively trained in aging populations? (B) Does training in WM subsidiaries lead to near-transfer effects on the central executive? These questions guide the hypotheses that (1) WM subsidiaries can be trained despite advanced age and (2) training WM subsidiaries can induce a near-transfer effect on the central executive.

METHODS

Study design

This study employs a quasi-experimental design to investigate the effects of training working memory (WM) subsidiaries on criterion and near-transfer tasks. Conducted in 2022 at a social care establishment for the elderly, the design included pre- and post-test measurements to assess changes in WM performance.

Participants and sampling method

Thirty older adults aged 60-83 volunteered to participate in the study. Participants were assisted living community residents or lived independently with their family members. None had prior exposure to cognitive training or were instructed in mnemonic techniques. Random assignment was used to allocate participants into two active training groups and one control group, ensuring a balanced distribution of age, education, and baseline cognitive performance as measured by the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE). Active Group 1 received 20 training days, active Group 2 received 25 training on the Cogmed program, and the remaining 10 formed the control group.

Participants were screened using inclusion criteria (age 60 and over with intact cognitive performance according to the MMSE) and exclusion criteria (neurodegenerative conditions, seizure disorders, history of head trauma, current anti-depression medication, and sensory impairments).

Control of confounding variables

Confounding variables such as educational level, general health, and daily activity were systematically recorded and controlled during data analysis. Educational differences were statistically adjusted using covariance analysis to isolate the effect of the WM training from educational background influences.

Data collection and study procedure

Criterion tasks

Forward digit span and Corsi blocks were used as criterion tasks. In the forward digit span task, participants were given a sequence of numbers at a rate of one per second and asked to tell them back immediately. The participant's performance on the forward digit span task was determined after two incorrect attempts at a difficulty level. Corsi blocks formed the second criterion task, in which the participants were required to tap a sequence of up to nine analogous blocks as they were initially tapped by the examiner. The Corsi task was discontinued when the participants failed to tap the blocks correctly within two trials at a level of difficulty.

Near transfer effect

A backward digit span task was used to detect near transfer effects of WM training. In the backward digit span task, each participant was required to repeat a sequence of numbers in reverse order, as offered by the examiner. The test stopped when the participants failed to recall the sequence reversely within two attempts at a level of difficulty.

The two adopted programs in the current study address WM subsidiaries. The first training program is conducted for 20 days at a rate of 30 minutes per session. Over 15 minutes, a set of animals' names must be tapped in the correct order when their silhouettes disappear. This task becomes so challenging when the silhouettes are displayed fast. Within the residual 15 minutes, nine panels (which sound like a computerized version of Corsi blocks) are displayed on the screen; the currently blinking ones must be serially tapped. The more the panels are tapped correctly, the more the task becomes challenging. The second training program is Cogmed. It was adapted to train WM subsidiaries across 25 days for about 15 minutes per session. The Cogmed light version contains exercises targeting simple information storage, not manipulating it.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were initially used to analyze the collected data and characterize the data set. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables. Comparisons of different scores were conducted using independent t-tests. Data analysis was performed using SPSS software version 21.0, with the significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical aspects

This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Ethics Review Board of the Department of Applied Psychology of the Faculty of Arts and Human Sciences.

RESULTS

As shown in Table 1, there were apparent differences between the active and control groups concerning years of formal education and MMSE scores.

Table 1. Sample characteristics.

Characteristics	Active group 1 (N=10)		Active group 2 (N=10)		Control group (N=10)	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Age	69.00	4.76	67.40	3.71	70.90	6.67
Educational level	4.50	5.14	8.10	4.70	5.10	5.66

MMSE	22.60	5.01	27.7	1.82	23.90	4.58
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Note: N = Number; M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation.

As shown in Table 2, there were differences between the groups with respect to performing the criterion tasks at the pre-test. Active group 2 had an initial advantage in forward digit span (M= 5.20, SD= 1.32) compared to active group 1 (M= 4.2, SD= 0.92) and the control group (M= 4.1, SD= 0.88). No remarkable differences were detected when performing the Corsi blocks task. The control group had a mean of 4.4 (SD= 0.77), while active group 1 had a mean of 4.2 (SD= 1.03) instead of 4.5 as a mean with a standard deviation of 0.97 for active group 2. The latter performed well on the backward digit span task at the pre-test (M= 3.7, SD= 0.67) compared to active group 1 (M=2.9, SD=1.45) and the control group (M= 2.3, SD= 1.42).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for the pre-test of the criterion and near-transfer tasks.

	Active group 1		Active group 2		Control group	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Criterion tasks						
Forward digit span	4.2	0.92	5.20	1.32	4.1	0.88
Corsi blocks	4.2	1.03	4.5	0.97	4.4	0.70
Near transfer						
Backward digit span	2.9	1.45	3.7	0.67	2.3	1.42

WM training slightly improved the forward digit span task at the post-test compared to the pre-test (see Tables 2 and 3). This relative improvement was only observed in active group 2, with a mean of 5.70 and a standard deviation of 1.06. Neither the active group 1 (M= 4.6, SD= 0.97) nor the control group (M= 3.9, SD= 1.10) improved on the forward digit span task after the training completion. Active group 2 had no significant improvement in performing on the Corsi blocks task at the post-test (M= 5, SD= 0.87) compared to active group 1 (M=4.7, SD= 0.67) and the control group (M= 4.6, SD= 0.84).

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for the post-test of the criterion tasks.

	Active group 1		Active group 2		Control group	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Criterion tasks						
Forward digit span	4.6	0.97	5.7	1.07	3.9	1.10
Corsi blocks	4.7	0.67	5	0.87	4.6	0.84

As illustrated in Table 4, there were differences between the groups concerning near transfer effects to the backward digit span task. By comparison with active group 1 (M=2.7, SD= 1.34), active group 2 displayed statistically significant performance on the backward digit span task at the post-test (M= 4.3, SD= 0.67), $t(9) = -3.67, p = 0.05$. There was no significant improvement for the control group (M= 2.4, SD= 1.65), $t(9) = 0.21, p = 0.83$ compared to active group 1 performance on the backward digit span task at the post-test. These results highlighted the efficiency of Cogmed in yielding improvement to WM tasks among an ageing population (Hyer et al., 2018).

Table 4. Descriptive statistics for the post-test of near-transfer task.

	Near transfer		t	df	p value
	M	SD			
Active group 1	2.7	1.34	0.51	9	0.61
Active group 2	4.3	0.67	3.97	9	0.05
Control group	2.4	1.65	0.21	9	0.83

Note: *The p-value refers to the Student t-test, and df = degrees of freedom.*

DISCUSSION

The present study addressed training WM subsidiaries in a sample of older adults to investigate its gains on criterion and near-transfer tasks. Statistical data shows that active group 2 had a slight advantage over the active group 1 and control group when performing criterion tasks, particularly forward digit span. Despite the limited advantage in performing the criterion tasks at the post-test, the current results and those reported in the literature confirm that WM remains plastic and trainable even in old age [12,16].

The present results indicate that training yielded more significant improvements in the near-transfer task than the criterion ones among active group 2. The latter outperformed active group 1 and the control group in performing the near-transfer task at the post-test. These results are congruent with those cited by Gao et al. [15], who found that training gains were much more evident in the transfer tasks than in the criterion ones. Differences in post-test results are attributable to individual characteristics that must be considered regarding WM training.

With this in mind, the current study highlights the impact of formal educational level on training gains. Active group, 2 advantage to the criterion and near transfer tasks at the post-test, is ascribed to higher years of formal education, regarded as a source of cognitive reserve in aging [17]. Similarly, age and crystallized intelligence may impact the training gains in both criterion and transfer tasks [18,19].

Near transfer effects can be induced by training any WM subcomponent. The results indicate that targeting WM subsidiaries generates near transfer effects to backward digit span as an untrained task tapping the executive aspect of WM. The present results are consistent with those reported in the literature [14]. Brum et al. [14] indicated that verbal WM training improves near-transfer tasks. Training effect sizes were observed in tasks of letter-number sequencing and digit span. Training gains maintenance lasted for 6 months after the intervention. Similarly, near-transfer effects can be induced in operation and reading span tasks devoted to measuring verbal WM [15,18]. These improvements may extend to the visuospatial component of WM.

Brum et al. [14] point out that verbal WM training generates near-transfer effects to visuospatial WM tasks despite being untrained. Brum [14] found near transfer effects to forward and backward spatial span tasks at the post-test and the follow-up, respectively. Moreover, the literature demonstrates that WM training positively influences the dot matrix as an untrained task [2,12]. Participants' performance on the dot matrix task improved across the assessment phases.

The current findings are incongruent with those obtained by Gao et al. [15]. The latter suggests that near-transfer effects cannot be generated without targeting the central executive. They claim training the central executive is more efficient than any other WM subcomponent in generating near-transfer effects to untrained tasks. Inconsistent with this view, Xin et al. [13] point out that the central executive benefits from updating WM training. In other words, training any WM subcomponent can lead to near-transfer effects, predicting improvements in untrained cognitive tasks [8].

Far transfer effects were not investigated in the present study. However, the available data indicates that it is possible to detect far-transfer effects from WM training among an aging population [12,19,20]. One study cited by Brehmer et al. [5] proves that far transfer effects may be observed in Raven progressive matrices tasks devoted to assessing reasoning. The post-test results demonstrate that participants' performance on the Raven progressive matrices task improved compared to the pre-test. These results were subsequently repeated in a study documented by Hering et al. [18], who emphasized that WM training induces far-transfer effects on global cognition.

Results obtained by Hering et al. [18] evince that WM training generates far transfer effects to the digit symbol task used to measure processing speed. Compared with the pre-test, the post-test results show increased performance among the participants on the digit symbol task. Far transfer effects to symbol tasks are considered an index of processing speed improvement. In line with these findings, Brum et al. [14] noticed that participants performed better on symbol search tasks across the assessment phases. It has become evident that the far-transfer effects of WM training are exclusive to reasoning and processing speed and executive functions that represent the higher-order cognitive processors.

A prior work cited by Borella et al. [12] shows far transfer effects extend to the Stroop task. As mentioned above, WM training enables participants to resist interference at the incongruent part of the Stroop task. In other words, inhibition is involved in the training-related gains at the post-test and the follow-up. In parallel, far transfer effects may also be observed in other executive functions' tasks, trial-making included.

Far transfer effects on the trial-making task were investigated by Brum et al. [14] in a group of older adults. Brum [14] noticed that participants' performance on the trial-making task improved in the post-test compared to the pre-test. Increased performance on the mentioned task indicates improvement in cognitive flexibility, which is positively influenced by WM training. Interestingly, training-related improvements in far-transfer tasks are identified along with brain changes [21-23].

Study limitations

Because of lack of time, the current study limited itself to measuring only the criterion and near transfer tasks, not the far transfer ones. These preliminary results should be followed up with research addressing near and far transfer effects of WM training and investigating training gains maintenance. Similarly, person-specific factors must be investigated to determine who benefits from WM training.

Implications for policymakers

The practical implications of this study on working memory (WM) training in older adults are significant for designing targeted cognitive interventions that can be implemented in various caregiving settings. Given the effectiveness of WM training in enhancing specific cognitive abilities, facilities providing elder care, such as nursing homes and day-care centers, can develop personalized memory training programs that cater to the needs of their residents. Moreover, this study suggests that even in advanced age, the brain retains considerable plasticity, implying that early intervention strategies might improve cognitive functions and slow down age-related cognitive decline. These findings could encourage families and caregivers to support and promote regular cognitive activities among the elderly, enhancing their quality of life and autonomy. Additionally, the results from this study can influence public policy, emphasizing the importance of funding cognitive training programs as a preventative measure to maintain and enhance mental health in the aging population.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study shows that training WM subsidiaries in older adults was associated with improving criterion and near-transfer tasks. The results obtained demonstrate that active group 2 slightly improved in performing the criterion tasks compared to active group 1 and the control group. As indexed on the near transfer task post-test results, active group 2 had an advantage over active group 1 and the control group. In fact, the active group 2 advantage in WM tasks is ascribed to a higher educational level.

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